

Orally Administered Insect Repellents: Approaches and Problems Related to the Search

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An active search for an insect repellent which could be administered orally has been progressing for several years. This work which was made possible by a grant from the Defence Research Board of Canada, is being conducted by the Ontario Veterinary College where accommodation is suitable for experimental animals.

The knowledge that some medicines and other substances are eliminated slowly through the skin or with the breath suggested the possibility of a systemic, orally-administered repellent. The pungent odour of hexachlorethane, for example, may be smelt in the breath of cattle several days after they have been treated with this drug for liver fluke disease. Another illustration is the characteristic and constant aroma of the habitual garlic eater. It seemed likely from this that the emanation of an insect repellent from the surface of the body for many hours, days, or even continuously would have endless possibilities. One principal advantage of a systemic over an externally applied repellent would be the elimination of repeated applications of oily, messy substances to the skin, with their associated irritating effect on the mucous membranes.

Briefly summarized, the work of our researchers in this field has included the administration to man or animals of all available substances which might reveal possibilities as orally-administered insect repellents. Each agent was introduced directly into the stomach of the experimental animal. However, in some instances, drugs, such as certain hormones, were necessarily administered by needle and syringe. The treated vertebrates were then exposed to mosquitoes for two or more days. Yellow fever mosquitoes or native species were used to check the effects of treatments. Test animals included guinea pigs, rabbits, rats, mice, hamsters and occasionally man.

The first substances tested were internal doses of every available insect repellent. In each case, as large a dose as was proved tolerable was given. A year or so later we tested many volatile oils on the assumption that good repellents are volatile compounds. Then followed a series of tests with sex and other hormones, selected alcohols, aldehydes, ethers, esters, acids, amides and phenols. We also tried other hydrocarbons, some alkaloids, ketones, oleo resins and salts, body deodorants and antihistamines. Miscellaneous tests on substances, alleged to keep humans free from insect attack, included the taking of vitamins in daily doses, the drinking of copious quantities of coffee and soya bean oil, and the eating of the odoriferous fruits of the ginkgo tree.

Our approach to this problem so far has been mostly empiric on the possibility that it might lead to results through a short cut. To this date we have had no success. In contrast to the empirical approach, a reasoned one would call for greater knowledge of the factors which attract or repel insects than is presently available. Also, we need to know more about vertebrate skin physiology and the nature and fate of substances administered internally from the time they reach the stomach to their chemical state on elimination through the skin.

One of the problems that had to be considered in comparative attraction tests was the possible rôle of biological variations in our test animals, such as age, sex and physiological condition (pregnancy, diet and blood sugar levels). For two years much time was spent studying these variables but none of them was found to make any significant difference in the attractiveness of animals, at least not to yellow fever mosquitoes.

We have always felt that the repellent action of the drugs tested may be limited inasmuch as small laboratory animals do not perspire as freely as large animals. However, we have little choice in our use of small animals because large animals are not economically practical for use in extensive tests. Experimental tests on man can only be done when the substances being tested are known to be safe. Incidentally, a time-consuming problem involved in this work is that of establishing safe dosage when the toxicity of a substance is not known. This question applied to many of the agents tested and to be tested as possible repellents for oral administration.

Various other problems confront the researcher in projects of this kind, chief amongst which is the maintenance of experimental animal colonies and mosquito colonies. Health, temperature, humidity and other similar matters all require constant consideration. The activity of mosquitoes varies with their age and from day to day. Consequently all experiments must be replicated, and position correction factors must be constantly considered when exposing treated animals to the insects.

In conclusion, may I suggest that future research in this area will be associated with better understanding of the physical and biochemical mechanisms which attract insects to their blood meals. This paper is presented with the hope that it may inspire others to join in the search for an effective systemic insect repellent.

DISCUSSION

W. H. R. LUMSDEN. In catches of mosquitoes on cows in Entebbe, Uganda, mosquitoes were taken on recumbent sick cows but not, on another occasion, on a recumbent cow anaesthetized with chloral hydrate.

A. A. KINGSCOTE. We have not used cattle in any of our tests but will certainly examine the possibilities of chloral hydrate.